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Subverting the Patriarchal Hegemony in Ismat Chughtai's "Lihaaf"

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Abstract:

Women's commodification and objectification perpetuate into social and cultural structures through "ho(mo)mosexual monopoly"(Luce Irigaray). Men dominate in women's exchange because of the valorization of men's needs and desires by socio-cultural institutions. Subsequently, the fulfilment of male desires becomes the norm which eventually leads to the subjugation of women and their bodies creating gender inequality. The systematic perpetration of patriarchal hegemony cages women within the notion of the feminine mystique too. As a consequence, women perceive themselves as the happiest while serving men as dutiful wives, altruistic mothers, and coquettish mistresses. For a critical understanding of pervasive patriarchal hegemony in social institutions, this paper attempts to reread Ismat Chughtai's "Lihaaf" through the critical lens of second-wave feminists Helen Cixous, Luce Irigaray, and Betty Friedan. The analysis also focuses on the language of women or *écriture féminine* which the female characters use in expressing their desires, and needs of their inner voice. Thus, the study urges the urgent necessity to acquire harmonious coexistence of genders in cultures by subverting the patriarchal hegemony.

Keywords: Ho(mo)mosexual monopoly, The Feminine Mystique, *Ecriture feminine*.

Do women's desires align with the male gaze? Do women seek validation from men? Moreover, more importantly, why do men in this overtly patriarchal society see the subjugation of women as necessary and inevitable? Undoubtedly, women have fared well fighting for their equal rights against patriarchy. However, Jenny Yang's recent survey about the gender distribution of total cosmetic surgical procedures worldwide 2018-2022, raises skeptical questions about women's liberation and freedom. According to Yang's report published on the *Statista*

website, women have taken 86% of the surgical cosmetic procedures worldwide while men show a slight rise of .3% in cosmetic surgical procedures (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1450230/gender-distribution-of-surgical-procedures>). The whopping rise in the women's ratio for cosmetic surgical procedures echoes the question, have women achieved freedom from the male gaze? Because women rushing for cosmetic surgical procedures resonate with Luce Irigaray's observation in, "Women on Market" (1985). According to Irigaray, "the society we know . . . is based upon the exchange of woman" and "we are told", "men circulate women among themselves" (170). Irigaray draws attention towards the underpinnings of the patriarchal control embedded in a socio-cultural matrix that permits women's exchange. Such exchange implies that women bear the burden of adapting according to the patriarchal norms so that they are included as objects for transactions among men. Is this not problematic when women change according to men's needs? Perhaps, women going for cosmetic surgeries are still affected by the social conditioning of adapting to men's desires to be a part of the grand exchange.

Also, men exchange women among themselves to fulfil their needs and desires. However, women's exchange occurs between men by men for men only. This sort of socio-cultural practice lays the foundation of "ho(mo)mosexual monopoly" (171). According to "ho(mo)mosexual monopoly," only men conduct women's transactions and men completely deny women's engagement during discussions and negotiations. Thus, women's exchange becomes purely the "men's business" and "ho(mo)mosexual monopoly" becomes central to the social-cultural patriarchal tradition that licenses men to perceive women's bodies as "utilitarian objects and bearers of value" (171-175). Consequently, men nurture the assumption of inherent powers that encourage them to identify and assign women and their bodies suitable roles that accord with men's "use, consumption, and circulation" (171). Therefore, this *a priori* prerequisite entailing the fulfillment of men's needs and desires subjects women to three roles "mother, virgin, and prostitute," (175) states Irigaray.

The categorization of women into three roles defines the requirement of feminine traits for women's utilization and socialization in patriarchal structures. For example, to fulfil motherly duties, men require the women type for nurturing, childbearing and caregiving. To satiate carnal desires, men highly desire the virgins until the consummation of marriage, and thereafter strict

monogamy is expected, even if men may take multiple wives (if the personal law allows). Further, after having the sense of sexual gratification from women's bodies, men reduce virgin women's worth to perform mundane tasks or domestic drudgery. Finally, to establish the ideals of masculinity and machismo, men require women as prostitutes to pander to their male ego. In this way, men establish patriarchal hegemony in the circulation of women that caters specifically to men's desires and wants.

Nevertheless, the question arises why is male monopoly rooted deeply? Regarding the perpetuation of men's monopoly in women's transactions, the anthropologist, Claud Levi Strauss, states that the social acceptance of men's "polygamous tendency" regardless of women's tendencies perpetuates the socialization of women as inert commodities (38). The discussion informs us that acknowledging men as inherently polygamous allows men to exchange and circulate women for utilization and subjugation to such an extent that women lose their identity as expressible and autonomous subjects. Further, Strauss explains the demand for women always exists whether "insufficient" or "scarce" because "these women would not be equally desirable due to the varying needs of men" (38). Again, men's whims and power govern women's demand and supply.

Ironically Irigaray informs, "The law that orders our society is the exclusive valorization of men's needs/desires, of exchanges among men" (171). Irigaray glosses the hypocrisy ingrained in the law because the law perpetuates male hegemony to oppress women. The law indoctrinates women to succumb to the needs of men only then does social harmony exist. Thus under the guise of law, men establish the principle of homosexual monopoly to perpetuate gender discrimination and women's commodification as "they serve as the possibility of and potential benefits" to men (172). Perhaps, therefore, women align their desires and seek validation from men because men assign value to women's bodies to circulate among men.

The paper attempts to analyse Ismat Chughtai's short story "Lihaaf" (1943) to reveal not only women's commodification but also the subversion of the "ho(mo)mosexual monopoly" that broke the glass ceiling back then. Besides subverting male control over women's bodies, Chughtai antagonizes the stereotyping of women into the specific roles of dutiful wives and obedient daughters resonating with the American author Betty Friedan's "The Feminine Mystique" (<https://www.h-net.org/~hst203/documents/friedan1.html>). Friedan argues that whether or not the

performance of domestic chores and familial duties provides happiness to women. But the patriarchal forces make women believe that it is natural and blissful for them to be in the role of dutiful wives, nurturing mothers and dutiful daughters. In "Lihaaf" Chughtai breaks this social illusion by depicting Nawab Saheb and Begum Jaan's dysfunctional marriage. Thus, this paper attempts to draw attention to the phallogocentric social culture apparatuses that commodify women and question feminine mysticism. Also, Chughtai dares to voice feminine desires rightfully through Begum Jaan's character triggering a social upheaval in the male-dominated society. Though summoned to the court for her obscene writings, Chughtai continued voicing feminine desires satirically through her femme-fatal characters who went against the grain.

The title of the short story "Lihaaf" ignites readers' curiosity to know what the quilt covers or uncovers. Generally, a quilt is an essential household requirement, which sometimes catches the attention, when something lies under the quilt. Soon after, a quilt becomes an object of discussion because it projects intriguing shapes. In the plot's context, the title "Lihaaf" makes sense because lihaaf dominantly connotes a veil or a haven under which women express their desires clandestinely. Perhaps a kind of veil that shows resistance to patriarchal norms and provides freedom of expression to fulfil their bodily desires. Also, the haven into which Begum Jaan escapes to get respite from her dysfunctional marriage. To emphasize the necessity of women's freedom of expression, the female protagonist, Begum Jaan's quilt, occupies the central position of an animate character that emanates noises and forms odd shapes at night. It veneers Begum Jaan's queer relationship with her masseuse Rabu. And under the quilt, Begum Jaan fulfils her desires and claims her body through the queer alliance in the Nawab Saheb's house. Does not the quilt become an objective correlative of the inner voice of Begum Jaan's liberation from her toxic marriage? Indeed, Chughtai uses the quilt as a trope to urge women to claim an unbridled free space by resisting the phallogocentric ideology. Truly, "Lihaaf" emerges as one of the texts that heralds the beginning of a new women's era expressing women's choices.

As in "Lihaaf", the sequence of events shows the transgression of women's thoughts from being a victim to an empowered *femme fatal* character. Chughtai has delved deeply into their predicament. The rereading of such texts engages in an open-ended discussion on different aspects of feminism which is both enlightening and insightful. Since, in contemporaneity, women face challenges in realizing whether they are doing lip service to feminist tenets or are they feminists

in the real sense. By employing the second-wave feminists' tenets of homosexual monopoly, feminism mystique and *écriture féminine*, the critical analysis aims to sensitize the readers that even after a long struggle, women are bound to abide by the patriarchal norms.

Is the marriage with Nawab Saheb an imposition on Begum Jaan? The marital alliance of Begum Jaan and Nawab Saheb can be seen as a consequence of the pervasive homosexual monopoly. Ho(mo)mosexual monopoly allows only men to control and govern women's transactions. Chughtai depicts the same when "Her [Begum Jaan's] poor parents agreed to marry her off to the Nawab who was of "ripe years" (36). In contrast, Begum Jaan was young and ravishing with a "marble body, rosy lips, and demure eyes" (38). Nevertheless, Begum Jaan's parents comply with the underlying principles of homosexual monopoly and agree to marry her off to an old wealthy Nawab Saheb inconsiderate of Begum Jaan's opinion. Thus, by rendering traits of an inert commodity on Begum Jaan, she naturalizes her circulation from father to husband in some kind of a grand exchange.

Moreover, the sole aim of passing Begum Jaan through marriage was to fulfil the needs of both the men—the father and the husband. Begum Jaan was a burden on her parents because of their weak financial conditions, they were unable to marry her off. But to maintain social order, the parents marry Begum Jaan to Nawab Saheb. And, Nawab Saheb agrees to marry her because he was sexually deviated. Nevertheless, Nawab agrees to marry Begum Jaan because, "Nawab Saheb had a strange hobby. . . . He kept an open house for students—young, fair and slender-waisted boys whose expenses were borne by him" (36). Thus, under the guise of marriage, Nawab continues practicing his queer hobby and he also acquires Begum Jaan (a mere commodity and slave) to run the errands of the household. Through this profitable transaction, Nawab conveniently defers societal punishment even though he violates one of the principles of "ho(mo)mosexual monopoly" which bars same-sexes from having sexual relations. On the contrary, Nawab becomes the epitome of a virtuous man because "No one had ever seen a nautch girl or prostitute" before or after marriage in his house (36). Thus marital pact maintains social harmony because "hom(m)osexuality is played out through the bodies of women" (172) meaning the women's exchange takes place for the benefit of men. And both, Nawab Saheb and the father commodify Begum Jaan for "use, consumption, and circulation"(171). The practice of "sociocultural endogamy" excludes the participation of women but allows men to dictate the lives of women in whichever way (172).

Through the same mechanism, Begum Jaan becomes the victim of the pervasive "ho(m)osexual monopoly" in the social institution of marriage and suffers both as a daughter and a wife from patriarchal oppression.

After getting married to an old but wealthy Nawab Saheb, Begum Jaan was certain of finding marital bliss in serving and performing the household chores according to the notion of the feminine mystique. But because of Nawab Saheb's sexual deviation, Begum Jaan feels shattered because she has no active role to play in social and cultural life but exists merely as the lost "infrastructure" (Irigaray 172). Although the old Nawab Saheb acquires young and beautiful Begum Jaan, he treats Begum Jaan as a trophy wife. (<https://www.nytimes.com/1994/05/01/magazine/on-language-trophy-wife.html>). He "tucked her away in the house with his other possessions and promptly forgot her" (36). Thus, Nawab Saheb completely neglected the existence of Begum Jaan for bodily pleasures but conversely, he didn't let Begum Jaan step out of his house. The atrocious behavior of Nawab disillusions Begum Jaan within the notion of feminine mysticism. And, she finds all the riches and comforts at her disposal worthless. Due to the lack of physical intimacy, she turns frail and unhappy. On the other hand, Nawab continues fulfilling his desires by calling young men to house under the guise of his so-called "strange hobby" (34). Although she has a husband and other felicities of domestic life, Begum Jaan feels miserable and alienated in her *haveli*. Thus, the disclosure of a dysfunctional marriage subverts feminine mysticism explicitly. In other words, while Begum Jaan is denied any fulfilment of her desires (which are not restricted to sexual desires, but also encompass a range of emotional and intellectual needs), Nawab Saheb not only has Begum Jaan at his disposal but also has an entire harem of sorts of young, nubile men who cater to his every sexual need, from need of another body, to need of sexual domination.

The "ho(m)osexual monopoly" puppets women in the ways and roles men desire and fancy. However, men have the prerogative of expressing and desiring pleasure and participation. In addition, these "phallocratic models" impose the three social roles on women as "Mother, virgin, prostitute" (186). Thus, "ho(m)osexual monopoly" coerces inequality among genders and perpetuates it into the social institution of marriage as well. In a social-cultural practice of marriage, women are less likely to express their feelings because of the entrenched patriarchal hegemony. And, the transgression subjects the females to bear discriminatory treatment. For

example, honor killing, burning live women, stone pelting till death and use of derogatory terms are some of the coercive practices to silence women. Therefore, women restrict and refrain from vocalizing about their feminine bodies and desires. To break the shackles of patriarchal control, Irigaray hopes that “by socializing differently the relation to nature, matter, the body, language, and desire” women may break free from the “ho(mo)mosexual monopoly” (191). Indeed, Chughtai’s twist in the plot of “Lihaaf” aligns with Irigaray’s suggestion.

Had Chughtai not portrayed Begum Jaan’s alternative way of finding solace in a queer relationship with masseuse Rabu, women would not think to break free from the clutches of “ho(mo)mosexual monopoly”. Indeed, “Lihaaf” is a pertinent text in contemporaneity to inform women to continue their fight to express themselves freely and to make their distinct choices apart from the three given categorical women’s roles since time immemorial. Further, by depicting Begum Jaan’s sexual urge, Chughtai declares women are not inert commodities but living beings capable of feeling, thinking, and acting who should have freedom over their bodies. Such writings enable women to experience the pleasure of asserting their choices for marriage, sexual preferences, abortions, and other aspects of women’s lives without any qualms.

Furthering the case, the French critic, Helen Cixous, argues in her much-celebrated essay “The Laugh of The Medusa” (1975) about devising a woman’s language or *écriture féminine*. Cixous argues:

Women must write through their bodies, they must invent the impregnable language that will wreck partitions, classes, rhetorics, regulations and codes, they must submerge, cut through, get beyond the ultimate reserve-discourse, including the one that laughs at the very idea of pronouncing the word ‘silence’ . . . Such is the strength of women that, sweeping away syntax, breaking that famous thread (just a tiny little thread, they say) which acts for men as a surrogate umbilical cord. (2049)

Cixous suggests women should invent *écriture féminine* or women’s language that conveys their feelings and bodily desires. Women who have been treated as objects should now express their feelings, wants, and wishes and not how they are forced to act and behave. To transgress the male discursive practices, women’s language should differ in their selection of words, sentence lengths, and syntax that can express specifically the emotions, feelings, stories, heartbreaks,

triumphs, and jubiliations of women and womanhood. Women's language or *écriture feminine* should be as unique as the umbilical cord which conveys only the essence of women's stories and feelings which have been silenced to maintain social and cultural order.

In "Lihaaf", Begum Jaan's deterioration in her physical appearance expresses her pain and anguish of isolation and neglect. The loss of her vigor and charm also suggests Begum Jaan's urge for sexual gratification:

When she watched through the drawing-room door the increasing number of firm-calved, supple-waisted- boys and delicacies began to come for them from the kitchen! Begum Jaan would have glimpses of them in their perfumed shirt and feel as though she was being raked over burning embers! (36)

When Begum Jaan faces the fact that her husband has queer interests, the notion of feminine mysticism of finding eternal happiness in domestic drudgery stings her. Because her dream of having fulfilled married life physically, emotionally, and mentally shatters. Also, the situation implies that Nawab Saheb will never desire Begum Jaan. And bound by conjugal vows, Begum Jaan will have to abstain from infidelity. Being torn between the conflict of feminine mysticism and bitter reality, Begum Jaan suffers from physical pain in the form of wretched itch and bodily discomfort. The anguish of living a virgin's life who is detestable and undesirable because of the queer habits of her husband consumes Begum Jaan with physical ailments. Nawab Saheb's betrayal devastates Begum Jaan completely nevertheless she also experiences torture in subduing her urges on seeing other men. Ironically, the underlying current of male dominance represses her desires. But, the vehement sexual yearnings of Begum Jaan get respite only when she starts receiving erotic massages from her masseur Rabu.

The patriarchy restricts women from expressing their sexual pining or they push women to veil their feelings. But the character of Begum Jaan dissents to succumb to the atrocities of male hegemony. Despite the indifferent treatment from Nawab Saheb, Begum Jaan tries to cope with her situation by wearing amulets, talismans and black magic. However, she fails to draw Nawab's attention and also fails to claim her right to pleasure. Left to cruel destiny, Begum Jaan accepts her physical desires as necessary as breathing and alleviates her vehement urges by using an alibi of a persistent itch which her masseuse, Rabu, could only soothe through erotic massages. In such

a patriarchal context, the character of Begum Jaan becomes the mouthpiece of women advocating for the necessity of fulfilling women's desires and wishes.

Begum Jaan's foray into suggested homosexuality, then, is not as much an act of sexual want, as an act of rebellion, of taking control of her own life and body, of reclaiming her space, within the suffocating confines of the Nawab's household. Interestingly, Nawab Saheb's *interest* in young boys is seen as a mark of taste and class. Thus, his little harem becomes a self-proclaimed kingdom where he plays out his fancies, and where he, the rich male, exploits the weaker sections of the society, weaker in terms of class, and weaker in terms of gender. The suggestion of a homosexual relationship between Begum Jaan and her masseur Rabu liberates women from the assigned roles, commodification, and feminine mysticism. By specifically portraying Begum Jaan's bodily cravings, Chughtai provides a voice to women's carnal desires and right to pleasure which have been throttled by phallocratic models of "ho(mo)sexual monopoly". By taking account of Begum Jaan's never-ending physical and mental pain of yearning, Chughtai declares women's right to sexual pleasure. The child narrator tells us that when Begum Jaan starts taking erotic massages under the quilt, it brings Begum Jaan back to life, "Her cheeks began to glow and she blossomed in beauty. It was special oil massage that brought life back to the half-dead Begum Jaan" (37). The Begum Jaan's transcendence represents that women possess desires and bodies. And, her incurable persistent itch alludes to women's unfulfilled desires. Her orgasmic exclamations announce the fulfilment of satiating her sexual desires. Does not her vocalized murmurings and whispers become the language for women or *écriture feminine* indicating sexual gratification? Also, when Begum Jaan feels guilty about being in a queer relationship with Rabbu, Rabbu outrightly rejects Begum Jaan's fear, and anxiety by appeasing her. And she snaps her rambling and slyly utters an oblique remark "These doctors are crazy . . . Theirs is nothing wrong with you. It's just the heat of the body" (37). Does not Rabu's innuendo subvert the perpetuation of men's monopoly through the women's language? Thus, it can be conceded that women should express themselves freely even if they have to invent a language specifically for women that allows women to express emotions in long sentences, vocalized pauses, and sexual innuendoes in contrast to the language of men who decree the expression of love and emotions. Thus, Rabu's intended pun asserts that women have animate bodies capable of responding to their instincts and cravings just like men. The characters of Begum Jaan and Rabu depict the fulfilment of women's needs and desires as essential as men's. Also, women's desires are neither triggered nor extinguished by men.

Women possess an instinctual body capable of responding and experiencing all sorts of emotions and desires.

The rereading of "Lihaaf" from the feminist perspective suggests that when patriarchal norms subjugate women's desires and needs, they should make efforts to break free from the entrenched oppressive male-constructed dispositions, discursive practices, structures and institutions such as marriage without having the guilt of liberation. As in the context of Begum Jaan, she transgresses from being an inert commodity to a wholesome woman when she vindicates her right to bodily pleasures and expressions of love by breaking the shackles of the patriarchal hush for sexual gratification in her marriage with queer Nawab Saheb.

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